

ALGORITHM FOR EDUCATION QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN NON-STATE SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS ON THE BASIS OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP

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Abstract. *Organization of educational processes in educational organizations is the most important component of their activity. It should be noted that the effectiveness of the management or pedagogical activities of any preschool educational organization is primarily determined by the quality of education in the organization, its level, and the extent to which it meets the educational needs of consumers.*

Keywords: *management, non-governmental preschool educational organizations, effectiveness.*

There are main directions of management activities of the heads of non-governmental preschool educational organizations based on PPP (public private partnership), which include planning the activities of the organization, providing personnel, establishing pedagogical processes as an educational organization and improving its quality, cooperation with the public and parents, mutually beneficial with partner organizations. may be areas such as relationship building. From the above opinion, it is understood that ensuring the quality and efficiency of education in a non-state preschool educational organization based on PPP, where pedagogical processes have been established, is one of the main directions of management activities.

N.Akhmedova, who conducted scientific research on improving the effectiveness of management activities of general secondary school leaders, in her research work, planning, organizing, controlling and objectively evaluating and encouraging the activities of subjects in the organization of pedagogical processes in the school, ensuring their quality and effectiveness, coordinating the management of leaders notes that it represents the activity [2].

According to the researcher G.A.Omanova, the permanent and regular personal participation of the management of the preschool educational organization in the quality management is the guarantee of success in the quality assurance process of the educational institution [3].

Professor M.A.Yuldashev emphasizes that a significant part of the responsibility for the quality of education falls on the management system and its creators, and the remaining part falls on the executors [4].

It should be noted that the effectiveness of the management or pedagogical activities of any preschool educational organization is primarily determined by the quality of education in the organization, its level, and the extent to which it meets the educational needs of consumers.

A number of opinions and approaches are put forward in the literature about quality, quality of education and its essence.

In the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language” it is stated that quality is a word that expresses a property, feature, quality, character, and that it expresses the meaning of the

characteristic that determines the degree of suitability of a product or work, how well it meets the set requirements [5].

Professor U.Inoyatov notes in his scientific research work that the main problems facing the education system today are, to one degree or another, related to the quality of education [6].

Pedagogical scientist M.A.Yuldashev emphasizes that the quality of education is the degree of acquisition of academic knowledge by students, as well as the formation of competencies in various spheres of life, readiness for lifelong learning, personal and professional development, and the level of stagnation of motivation [4].

The authors of the work “Monitoring the quality of education in the school” S.E.Shishov and V.A.Kalneylar stated that the main task of the quality of education is to determine the conformity of the current state and social results of education with the requirements of society, the development of civil and professional qualities of a person, and its quality is a participant in the educational process. states that it is expressed through the satisfaction of the parties with the educational services provided by the institution and the level of achievement of the goals and tasks set in education [7].

Based on the above analysis, it can be noted that quality management of pre-school education is management organized to implement pre-planned goals and tasks of education and ensure achievement of guaranteed results by applying management functions.

In this place, the goal of the educational process was to create appropriate conditions for the physiological and intellectual development of the students of preschool educational organizations, for the formation of appropriate competencies in them.

In order to ensure the quality of education in pre-school education organizations, regulatory documents provide for the implementation of control over compliance with the requirements of the “State Standard of Pre-school Education and Education”

It is understood from the above that this normative document does not indicate the types and mechanisms of control of the quality of education in non-state preschool educational organizations.

Therefore, it is the need of the hour for PPP-based non-governmental pre-school education organizations as business entities to be one of the most interested parties in the appropriate level of education quality.

Based on the theoretical analysis of the quality of education, its evaluation criteria, methods, and quality management, an algorithm for managing the quality of education was developed in a non-governmental preschool educational organization based on PPP (Fig. 1).

In order to implement the sequence of actions presented in this algorithm, based on the management functions, the current state of the quality of education in the organizations selected as test objects, the conditions created for the educational process were analyzed, and the internal and external factors affecting the quality were determined.

Figure 1. Algorithm of quality management of education in non-governmental preschool educational organization based on PPP

Non-state pre-school education organizations based on PPP to increase children’s coverage, provide educational processes with the necessary tools to ensure the quality of education, create a developmental environment, construction, construction and mathematics, plot-role games and dramatization, language and speech, science, art , the presence and equipment of music and rhythmic centers, the availability of sufficient conditions in the building, territory, training rooms and dormitories aimed at maintaining children's health and physiological development, was given great importance.

The demands and needs of parents, who are the main and most important consumers of preschool education services, were studied. Before the beginning of the academic year, questionnaires were conducted among parents, and their opinions on improving the educational processes in the non-governmental preschool education organization based on PPP, and their expectations from preschool education in the near and long term were studied. Also, partner organizations, including at the beginning of the new school year

The condition of children’s preparation for school education was analyzed with primary school teachers, psychologists, and parents of general secondary schools where former pupils who have reached the 1st grade receive education.

As a result of this study and analysis, a social order was formed regarding the educational process in a non-governmental preschool educational organization based on PPP, variable educational programs, additional educational services (science and sports clubs) based on the needs of parents were determined.

Based on the formed social order, in cooperation with the organization's founder, director and pedagogical team, the main goals and tasks of the non-state preschool education organization based on PPP were determined, and short-term and future plans were developed.

The goal of the non-governmental preschool education organization based on PPP is to form and develop the general and developmental competencies of the students, and to create the appropriate conditions for this process.

As mentioned above, the quality of teaching staff is important in ensuring the quality of education, and one of the most important tasks facing the head of the organization is to attract citizens with relevant professional knowledge and qualifications to work, to improve their professional skills, and to ensure continuous professional development.

During the experimental work, we organized educational seminars in cooperation with the district (city) preschool education departments based on the “State standard of preschool education

and upbringing”, “State requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age”.

Organization of educational processes in educational organizations is the most important component of their activity. Educational processes in non-governmental preschool education organizations based on PPP are carried out based on the “State standard of preschool education and upbringing”, “State requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age”, “State curriculum of preschool education organization” [1] and the model curriculum of preschool education. is increased.

PPP-based non-governmental preschool education organizations have the right to use variable educational programs approved by the Ministry of Preschool Education in the educational process. This right helps non-governmental preschool educational organizations based on PPP to meet the needs of customers and find a place in the market of educational services based on strong competition based on the development and implementation of a varied curriculum in accordance with the formed social order.

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